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Multicultural Approach in Musical Education through the Online Course Based on MOODLE

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Abstract

Ethnic cultural traditions take an important role in the process of a well-rounded and spiritually developed personality. Diverse types of folklore creativity, customs, rituals determine the moral and aesthetic potential of each ethnic group, being an integral component of national as well as universal culture. Therefore, it is particularly important to use a multicultural approach for education that allows person to learn the culture of their people, and successfully interact with other ethnic cultures.

Multicultural approach in education is a trend of preparation for the social, political and economic conditions that persons experience in complex human environment.

The purpose of the research is to substantiate the pedagogical capacity of a multicultural approach in a process of teacher-musician education by means of an online course.

In the course of the research, the principles of a multicultural approach in the education of a teacher-musician were studied:

- Deep learning of own culture through others;
- Comparing of different musical cultures for getting new knowledge.

It also revealed the pedagogical potential of a multicultural approach in the process of the teacher-musicians` education by means of the online course " Volga region peoples` music ", which develops a set of knowledge, performing skills in the field of vocal folklore traditions, is aimed at educating the moral and spiritual qualities of a person by comparing different cultures and exchanging experience between them.

Key words: multicultural approach, teacher-musician, ethnoculture, online course, digital technologies.

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Introduction

The conditions of modern life of the World's population are characterized by the expansion of cross-cultural relationships between peoples and the strengthening of multicultural trends. At the same time, on the one hand, there is a danger of peoples losing their cultural identity, which is possible due to rapid changes in the socio-cultural environment. On the other hand, another trend is associated with the processes of localization and regionalization of national and ethnic revival of cultures and peoples-in the awareness of their original cultural and historical path, a sense of rootedness in their socio – cultural space, in the correlation of their fate with their small homeland, country, religion, its past, present and future.

In this context the problem of educating the younger generation on the basis of a multicultural approach, which involves relying on the cultural traditions of various peoples and local groups, is particularly relevant. The deep study of ethno-pedagogical experience impossible without the process of tolerant person formation and the purpose to adopt of spiritual values as personal as well as without other people who want to discover a shared and unique culture of each ethnic group. This process also includes as mandatory the study of ethno-cultural traditions in the educational process, which primarily depends on the optimal interaction of all structures of the educational system.

The modern educational space cannot function without relying on multicultural values, which include achievements and traditions of different regions, when a multicultural approach becomes an important direction for the development of the education system, which is based on the dialogical nature of the functioning and improvement of culture.

Today, one of the priority directions in the implementation of a multicultural approach is the use of digital technologies in the educational process. A significant factor of information resources is the availability of information, which significantly expands the possibilities of the educational process. Computer equipment and software allow for the collection, storage, processing and transfer of information, digital technologies provide interactive methodological support for the learning process and the activities of educational institutions. An important part of the application of digital technologies in education is distance learning, which does not depend on the time and location of the student.

In this regard, the author's experience in implementing the treasures of national cultures of the Volga region on the basis of a multicultural approach by means of digital technologies in the Higher school of national culture and education named after Gabdula Tukai of the Institute of Philology and Intercultural Communication of Kazan (Volga) Federal University is offered, since the study of regional musical traditions is one of the most important components of professional training of future teachers-musicians at the University, which is due to the importance of developing future specialists' readiness to reach educational purposes using the achievements of national and regional cultures (Nurgayanova, Karkina, & Mena, 2019).

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the research is to substantiate the teaching capacity of a multicultural approach in the process of educating a teacher-musician by means of an online course.

Literature review

Multicultural education had become an important trend in from the late 1970`s in American teacher education and in other countries include Russia. Some researchers highlight its “central feature of the world in which we live” (Seglow, 2003). Despite the fact of ignoring of this approach for many years, such problems as struggle by African-Americans for full political inclusion, the confederalism adopted by several European states to accommodate linguistic and religious diversity and the multicultural policies adopted by Australia and Canada in the 1970x helped to realize its great mean for world (Seglow, 2003).

The term “multiculturalism” refers to the political, legal and philosophical strategies that emerged after World War II to accommodate this new-found social diversity. Society that called as “multicultural” is to claim that it contains multiple cultural groups rather than just one (Ashcroft & Bevir, 2019). Multicultural approach in education is a trend of preparation for the social, political and economic realities that individuals experience in culturally diverse and complex human encounters (Davidman & Davidman, 1988).

The musical culture of the Volga region reflects the enormous artistic and ethnopedagogical potential accumulated over many centuries. The authors have been studying the ethnocultural traditions of the Volga region in the frameworks of intercultural dialogue, conducting an analysis based on historical and pedagogical principles of the main range of folklore genres, musical instruments, and folk festivals for a number of years (Nurgayanova, Batyrshina, & Ahmetova, 2015). Thus, the features of the traditional culture of the Mordvins-Karatai were revealed (Nurgayanova, Karkina, & Gluzman, 2017), ethnographic groups of the Tatar people: Tatar-Kryashen (Akhmetova & Nurgayanova, 2016), Tatars-Mishars (Karkina, Nurgayanova, & Kaur, 2019), Tatar-chat (Martynova et al., 2018).

Based on the results it is possibly to think about the possibility of using the broadest educational and educational potential of local ethnic groups in the development of inter-ethnic spiritual ties, fostering tolerance, expanding competence in issues of intercultural interaction.

The largest researchers who studied Volga region musical cultures are Brazhnik (2002), Kondratyev (1999), Maklygin (2000), Radzetskaya (2013), Yakovlev (2001), etc. In their works, they characterize the musical language of the peoples of the region, consider genre systems of song folklore, and study traditional tools.

According to research of Valiahmetova, Salpykova, & Nurgayanova (2014) the tolerance of future music teacher can be improved in the educational process in multicultural educational environment by means of music.

According to the research of Zakirova & Kamalova (2016) multicultural education contributes to the improvement of a person who is ready to live in a multicultural and multi-ethnic environment, but at the same time preserving their socio-cultural identity, striving for respect and understanding of other cultures, that can live in harmony with representatives of other cultural and ethnic communities.

Methodology

Methods:

- analysis and synthesis of philosophical, methodological, pedagogical, psychological, historical, scientific and methodological, ethnopedagogic, ethnographic, art history, musical and pedagogical, archival literature;
- generalization and study of educational software and pedagogical documentation;
- pedagogical analysis of ethnocultural traditions;
- observation, questioning, conversations, testing, surveys, interviewing;
- study and generalization of pedagogical experience;
- quantitative and qualitative analysis of the results obtained using statistical methods, digital and information technologies.

Theoretical and empirical methods allow to analysis of the state of development of the problem, theoretically substantiate the basic concepts of research, lead to the accumulation of theoretical and factual material, the definition of research methodology based on analysis, theoretical understanding, systematization and generalization of materials on the selected problem, the development and implementation of specific scientific, methodological and practical recommendations.

The experimental base of the research was the Kazan (Volga) Federal University.

The research work was carried out in three stages:

The first stage included analysis of the existing musical-pedagogical, historical, art, ethnographic, folkloric, literary, philosophical, methodological, pedagogical, psychological, methodological, ethnopedagogical, archival literature was conducted pedagogical analysis of a musical tradition of peoples of the Volga region; was selected problem, purpose, methods, a plan of study.

At the second stage was put the development of educational materials, manuals, special courses, and electronic educational resources. At the third stage, the developed materials were introduced into the process of remote training of future music teachers using MOODLE elements.

Results

The educational process of the Higher school of national culture and education named after G. Tukai and IFMK KFU is carried out in accordance with the requirements of state educational standards of higher professional education, where, along with the Federal component of the basic and elective courses, teaching, music theory and performance training is the development of folk music traditions of the region, the composer's creative work is of theoretical and pedagogical analysis. Students, along with studying samples of classical and modern music, are offered in-depth theoretical and practical development of musical folklore traditions of the Volga region peoples.

The learning process currently reflects the implementation of a competency-based approach. According to the provisions of the main educational program, the graduate must possess universal, general professional and professional competencies, thanks to which future teachers-musicians are prepared for a tolerant perception of social and cultural differences, a careful attitude to the historical heritage and cultural traditions of different peoples, the ability to use the opportunities of the regional cultural educational environment for organizing cultural and educational activities.

The ability to perceive, artistic and value comprehension and professional and creative use of the achievements of the multi-ethnic musical culture of the Volga region is reflected in the curriculum, which provides excursions into the problems of intercultural cooperation of the peoples of the Volga region, allowing you to delve into various aspects of national cultures.

The development of ethnomusicological traditions of the region is based on the lecture courses of the educational module "Music of the Volga peoples", which includes such disciplines as "Music of the Volga peoples", "Spiritual origins of musical art", "Musical folklore", "the Use of folklore in musical education", "History of Tatar music", "Tatar musical Ethnography", "Fundamentals of Tatar traditional vocal art", etc.

Within the framework of these courses, based on the use of methods of musical and theoretical analysis, we analyze the fret, rhythmic features, genre composition of folk tunes, instrumental plays, components of religious ritual actions, such as the traditions of book singing among Muslim Tatars, choral singing in the culture of orthodox Kryashen Tatars and other ethnic groups of the Volga region. At the same time, not only special, but also common elements of the musical system are revealed: angemitonic pentatonic, quantitative rhythm, and identical genres of song folklore are revealed.

One of the most significant elements in the process of professional training of future music teachers is the use of the pedagogical potential of the ethnomusicological traditions of the region in the content of musical disciplines and methodological aspects in the system of General and additional music education. In the course of preparing for teaching practice, the author examines the peculiarities of conducting music lessons, extracurricular musical and educational work, and organizing children's folklore groups using regional musical heritage.

An important component in the process of mastering the complex of professional knowledge necessary for a future teacher-musician is the development of online courses MOODLE, because today, along with traditional forms, the most urgent requirement of the educational process is the use of distance learning.

The use of digital format in the course of teaching the discipline "Music of the Volga region peoples" gives a number of advantages of saturation of educational information through the use of multimedia equipment and programs for creating educational tools (digital educational resources, electronic textbooks, training programs, presentations, technologies for knowledge control, tests, etc.), modeling objects and situations.

By the means of digital technologies, students have additional opportunities to obtain and organize information, remote access to reference resources and electronic libraries.

The content of the discipline "Music of the peoples of the Volga region" covers the following areas: musical folklore, musical culture and professional music of the peoples of the Volga region.

In the process of mastering the theme "Musical folklore of the Volga peoples", the main stages of the formation of the traditional culture of the indigenous ethnic groups of the Volga region in the development of the Volga-Ural historical and ethnographic region are considered, ethnographic sources, folklore materials, syncretic genres of artistic culture are studied.

An important part of the discipline includes knowledge of material and spiritual culture, ethnomusicological traditions, customs, rituals, mythological representations and religious beliefs of Finno-Ugric (Mordvins, Mari, Udmurts), Turkic (Tatars, Chuvash) peoples, as well as the Russian population of the Volga region.

The section "Professional musical culture of the Volga region" covers the period of development of musical culture of the Volga region in the twentieth century. Here students get acquainted with the creative portraits of the first concert musicians, the authors of the first musical works, the work of professional composers of Chuvashia, Mari-El, Mordovia, Udmurtia, Tatarstan, and musical culture in the Volga region at the present stage.

The online course materials are accompanied by video lectures with a set of slides and presentations that can be downloaded for local viewing. The passed topics are fixed by practical tasks. Verification of the knowledge obtained is carried out using tests, where points are awarded for each correct answer.

The result of mastering the discipline, including in a distance format, is knowledge about the main stages of musical culture formation of the Volga peoples; modern cultural processes in the Volga region; features of folk and professional musical culture of the main ethnic groups of the Volga region; leading personalities and the most outstanding phenomena in the history of musical culture of the Volga region.

The study showed that the use of digital technologies forms students' ability to develop and implement ethno-cultural traditions, an ethno-regional component in the cultural and educational process, and conduct research in this area.

Possession of skills of analysis and interpretation of cultural forms and practices characteristic of the musical culture of the Volga region peoples will allow students to fully apply systematized cultural and historical knowledge in their future professional activities in educational institutions of General and additional musical education.

Discussions

In the XXI century, more and more attention is being paid to solve the problems of the existence and preservation of ethnomusicological traditions, song folklore in modern times, and to the study of traditional folk culture in its local manifestations. In the modern socio-cultural situation, the existence of song and musical folklore of peoples, and in particular of the Volga region, is one of the special carriers of historical memory, a representation of the cultural and historical fate of the people. Therefore, today the most important tasks in the field of education and culture are not only the tasks of preserving cultural heritage, but, above all, its use and actualization. As the research has shown one of the priority directions in the implementation of the multicultural approach is the use of digital technologies in the educational process.

The model of a complex system of music education aimed at broadcasting traditional culture in an organic combination with highly artistic samples of modern music in the conditions of functioning of the digital educational environment was

presented in their work by Gorbunova, & Plotnikov (2017). This model is based on the best traditions of Russian multinational culture and highly artistic samples of modern music, designed for implementation in the areas of General basic (and primary) and additional, inclusive, professional pedagogical, professional music, continuous education. On the basis of the implementation of the educational process in a digital educational environment, the authors see the creative potential that a person is able to reveal in himself, competently using the capabilities of information-computer and music-computer technologies.

Petrova and Bondareva (2019) in their research analyzed the stages of digitalization and the emergence of new digital technologies that have a huge pedagogical potential. Scientists, considering the problem of digitalization and digital technologies in education, point to the importance of spreading such educational technologies as online courses, which are provided by modern universities for all students. Such educational technologies as mass educational training courses applied remotely will help students to study in any convenient way for them and will allow them to receive qualified training in a specific field of study.

Online learning in a digital educational environment involves several types. The first type is synchronous learning, when an online lesson involves electronic interaction between a student and a teacher at a specific time. The second type includes asynchronous courses, where the teacher puts out theoretical material, as well as tasks for independent work, tests to check the learned information on the course. Students can take asynchronous online courses at any time they want. As a rule, today in the educational process, a mixed type of training is used, combining classroom work with an interactive online lesson.

It is important to point out that students currently have the opportunity to receive educational information from personal digital devices (smartphones, tablets, etc.).

Conclusion

The expansion of knowledge about the development of ethno-cultural traditions in pedagogical and cultural aspects based on the use of online courses, allows us to talk about the broad possibilities of studying ethno-cultural traditions based on the digital technologies.

Computers and multimedia programs used in the educational process, as well as distance learning, allow us to speak about the wide opportunities for studying ethnic and cultural traditions based on a multicultural approach using modern digital technologies:

- activization of the state of readiness and openness to the perception of other cultures and in the process of their study, as well as a deeper understanding of their own culture;
- revealing the pedagogical potential of ethnocultural traditions of the Volga region;
- identification of historical and pedagogical trends in the development of ethno-cultural traditions within the framework of integration of ethno-cultural, intercultural and multicultural components;
- manifestation of regional and local features of the formation of ethno-cultural traditions in a multicultural space;

- influence of traditional folklore (labor, family, ritual, holiday traditions, chants and instrumental plays) on the formation of moral and aesthetic views, spiritual qualities of a person capable of interethnic, intercultural and interfaith dialogue;
- the formation of a complex of knowledge, performing skills, extant folk genres based on the use tradition passed on from generation to generation, ethnic and cultural heritage;
- deepening knowledge in the field of ethnopedagogics through the study of ethno-cultural traditions using digital technologies that currently provide a cultural link between generations, the broadcast of socio-cultural, spiritual, and aesthetic experience, and the introduction of the individual to universal and ethnic values;
- identification of the prospects for the use of digital technologies in identifying the characteristic genre and style features of traditional folklore, poetic and musical content, historical origin, place in the system of rites, in performing and pedagogical practice.

Recommendations: identification of the main areas of application of digital technologies:

- access to reference resources and electronic libraries containing information about different cultures and traditions;
- visualization of information using multimedia equipment and programs for creating presentations;
- modeling of objects and situations in order to study them;
- organization of online communication between users;
- creation of educational tools for the educational process (electronic textbooks, training programs).

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